

Proceedings

of

National Workshop on

Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture

Theme- Greening the cities, utilising the waste, meeting the needs and servicing the environment.

2nd March, 2013 at ITC Windsor, Bangalore

**Confederation of Horticulture
Associations of India (CHAI)**

249, Sector 18 A, Dwarka, New Delhi – 110075, India

Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India

New Delhi

Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India, (CHAI) New Delhi is the consortium of agricultural professionals committed for the development of agriculture/horticulture by providing solution to the problems utilising the services of talented experts in the field of agriculture/horticulture and disseminate the knowledge for the development. In the scenario of increasing hunger, malnutrition and challenges of climate change, technology-led agriculture has assumed greatest significance for food, nutrition, healthcare and environmental services, and above all, the economic development. In this context, a forum, which brings scientists, associations, corporate sectors, institutes and organisations, farmers and various stakeholders together, to work in mission mode with set goals and objectives was felt essential for addressing the challenges, hence, the CHAI was established in the year, 2010. The CHAI is committed to the furtherance of agriculture / horticulture research, education and technology-led development.

Goals and Objectives of the CHAI is to play a catalytic role, in addressing the concern of food and nutritional security, through interventions of technology-led agriculture / horticulture development. The mission is to bring synergy among different societies/associations, experts and entrepreneurs to encourage effective participation of all the stakeholders for accelerating the economic growth through technological interventions and human resource development. Main objectives of the CHAI are furtherance of agriculture / horticulture through improved cooperation by integrating scientific study, education and knowledge exchange of biological, ecological, environmental, sociological and economic issues that affect agriculture / horticulture, to catalyse the efforts of development by creating associations for interaction among all agriculture / horticulture societies/ associations, growers, entrepreneurs, policy planners and activists through consultations, organisation of seminars, conferences, meetings, national dialogue and trainings. The CHAI also aims to establish, promote, run, maintain and support the community for the promotion in advancement of agriculture/horticulture and to serve as an apex organisation concerned with promotion of agriculture / horticulture, having linkages with various commodities / input organisations, institutes and Governmental and Non-Governmental organisations; the confederation is also committed to establish education and training institutions for human resource development and skill up gradation; It recognises the services of people in horticulture through incentives, awards and encourage the participation in national and international events; to establish educational and research institutions and advise (consultancy institution) Government and others for building human resources; and to take up all the activities, deemed to be fit for achieving economic growth through agriculture / horticulture development.

ACTIVITIES

- CHAI has successfully organised national and international conferences, workshops and national consultation and has serviced in education and providing solutions to the problems
- Awards and fellowships is instituted to recognise the contribution of scientists and other stakeholders in the research and development in the country and also abroad
- The Confederation has instituted various awards, which includes "Lifetime Achievement Award; Dr. R.S. Paroda Award for Excellence; B H Jain Award for technology-led development; Honorary Fellowship; CHAI Fellowship.
- CHAI has instituted overseas fellowship for training and participation in conference for meritorious members.
- CHAI publishes International Journal of Innovative Horticulture (IJH) and also publish newsletters and books.

STRENGTH OF CHAI

- The CHAI has wide spectrum of experts, who are enrolled as fellow to support the technology led development.
- The Chairman, having held the position of DDG, ICAR; Vice-Chancellor, RAU, Pusa; Horticulture Commissioner, is known nationally and internationally in the field of research, education, and development. He has skills in water management, nutrient management, quality seed and planting material production and above all coordination, planning and execution of projects of par excellence.
- Fellows of CHAI has expertise in various aspects of agriculture / horticulture. Besides, more than 100 experts in different fields from India and abroad are enrolled.
- CHAI has offices in Delhi, Patna, Bangalore and also in Dubai to attend all types of consultancy for business solution options.
- The CHAI is a non-profitting Company thus the organisation has the motto of service.
- The network of CHAI, expertise of skilled fellow and standing experts makes the Confederation to offer consultancy for modernizing agriculture / horticulture and serve the nation

CHAI can be contacted on the following address to develop project, programmes and business solutions.

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PROCEEDINGS OF NATIONAL WORKSHOP ON
URBAN AND PERI-URBAN HORTICULTURE

Theme- Greening the cities, utilising the waste, meeting the needs and servicing the environment .

2nd March, 2013 at ITC Windsor, Bangalore

Compiled and Edited by:

**H P Singh
H P Sumangla
P Chowdappa
Babita Singh**

**Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India
New Delhi**

Acknowledgment

Organiser of the National workshop on urban and peri-urban horticulture, the Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India acknowledges the support provided for the conduct of successful event in the terms of technical content and participation, which has provided an insight for resilient UPH. We extend our sincere thanks to dignitaries, scientists, policy planners, industry and all the stakeholders for their participation and technical inputs. Sponsorship provided by the Director, Department of Horticulture, Lalbagh and Vice-chancellor, UHS, Bagalkot is thankfully acknowledged.

Dr. H P SINGH, FNAAS

The Founder and Chairman

Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India (CHAI)

(Formerly, DDG (Hort.), ICAR;

Vice-Chancellor, RAU,Pusa, Bihar Horticulture Commissioner, MOA;

Dean, Agriculture, GBPUA&T, Pantnagar

Chairman, Coconut Development Board, Kochi; Director, NRCB, Trichy)

Proceedings

Recognising that, global population will reach 10 billion by the end of 2050, of which, about 70 percent of people shall reside in urban and peri-urban area, there is a global concern to meet their needs for food, nutrition and eco-environment. In this context **Urban and peri-Urban Agriculture (UPA)** is emerging as one of the options, and many international organizations are working with national partners to address the

issues, which calls for accelerated efforts. Initiatives to create awareness was taken by National Academy of agricultural sciences (NAAS), by organizing a brain storming session, convened by Dr H P Singh, then the DDG, ICAR. A policy framework was developed and policy document was published, which identified the urgency for the development of UPA. Considering that, horticulture has to play a pivotal role in UPA, for greening the cities and towns, meeting the needs of fresh produce, utilising home waste and above all to service the environment,

A National Workshop on Urban and Peri-urban Horticulture, was organized at ITC Windsor, Bangalore, on 2nd March, 2013 by the Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India (CHAI), a consortium of professionals, committed to the development of agriculture/horticulture, by providing solutions to the problem, utilising the services of talented experts, and disseminate the knowledge for the

development. Bangalore unit of CHAI is credited for the successful conduct of this workshop, which was attended by over 80 delegates representing research organizations, developmental agencies, industries, farmers and nurserymen. The workshop was conducted in 5 technical sessions and concluded with panel discussion leading to development of strategic action plan and policy to address the issues of urban and peri-urban horticulture (UPH).

Introductory session

Introductory session of the workshop chaired by Dr H P Singh, the Founder and Chairman, CHAI, brought a focus to the subject for deliberations and discussion. Dr P Rethinam, President, Southern region of CHAI, welcomed the distinguished guests and participants and highlighted the needs for the development of urban peri-urban horticulture, to cater the needs of nutritional requirements of urban population and effective management of solid wastes, and to enhance

the family income. Dr A.S. Sidhu, Director, IIHR, Bangalore, in his address stressed the importance of vegetables in peri-urban horticulture to safeguard the nutritional requirements of urban population and suggested for the development of technologies to produce fresh vegetables and mushroom scientifically to compliment the interest of urban population. He also informed about initiatives taken by the IIHR for UPH.

Dr. N.K. Krishna Kumar, DDG (Hort.), ICAR, New Delhi, in his inaugural address, emphasized the need for development of organic farming technologies suitable in urban horticulture to safeguard against pesticide residues and appreciated the efforts of CHAI in organizing the national workshop to deliberate and discuss this important topical issues of global concern. He also released a book, **Urban and**

Peri-Urban Horticulture - a perspective, on the occasion joined by other dignitaries on the dais Dr. Prem Nath, Chairman, PNAS Foundation, Bangalore, in his introductory, explained the concept and global initiatives of UPA and informed about the role of FAO and PNAS Foundation in UPA, which is essential to safeguard the interest of the urban peri-urban population and to compliment the needs of food and nutrition. He said that urban horticulture can play a vital role in generating income by the involvement of family members, and lead stress free life. He congratulated the CHAI for organizing the workshop on such a topical issue and expressed his satisfaction for the initiatives taken in India.

Dr. H.P. Singh, Former DDG (Hort.), ICAR, New Delhi, in his presidential remarks, Chairman, CHAI in his presidential remarks, explained about the rapid urbanization, wherein 65 percent of people may live in cities by 2050, bringing many challenges, which need attention and, UPH is one of the options. He briefly outlined the genesis of the workshop and expected outcome. He gave an

overview of the technical programme and explained about the CHAI. The Chairman also stressed upon the strategies to overcome the problems associated with urbanization, particularly poverty alleviation, nutritional security, management of pollution, utilization of wastes and health of urban population. To resolve these issues, he stressed for the promotion of UPH. Dr Chowdappa, while thanking the dignitaries briefly explained the activities of CHAI, Karnataka unit, and hoped that outcome of the workshop would be a guiding force for the promotion of UPH.

TECHNICAL SESSION I

Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture for Greening the Cities

The first technical session was chaired by Dr. H. P. Singh, Chairman, CHAI. Dr. N. L. Patel Dean, NAUT, Nausari and Dr. N. K. Srinivash Rao, Emeritus scientist, IIHR, Bangalore co-chaired the session. Two keynote lectures were delivered by Mr Robert Fernandez and Dr Prem Nath respectively. Mr. Robert Fernandez in his presentation, entitled **“Environmental challenges and emerging Landscape solutions”** talked about influx of growth in the cities which has impacted the infrastructure. Unless it is addressed with great caution, keeping in mind a pace of growth, it will be affecting sustenance. Creation of water harvesting zones are needed in the cities.

Green building is an important aspect of urban landscape and tree spade is one of the emerging landscape solutions where focus will be on conservation of the environment, while tree banks is another emerging landscape mitigation technique for basic and fundamental elements of urban and peri-urban horticulture. In the next keynote lecture, entitled **“Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture - A Global Perspective”**, Dr. Prem Nath discussed about UPH.

He said that, Urban and peri-urban horticulture which is a necessity rather than a demand and has become a key component of the survival strategies. UPA could be a source of employment and has the potential to improve the nutritional security of urban residents. Factors for success and sustainability of UPH were also discussed. Horticultural products @400g/person/day can prevent non-communicable diseases and improve the health. The session also developed a roadmap for UPH and suggested for initiatives in integrated manner involving all the stakeholders.

TECHNICAL SESSION II

Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture for environmental services

The second technical session was chaired by Dr P Rethinam, former Executive Director, APCC, Jakarta. Dr M R Hegde Principal Scientist, IIHR and Dr Kariyanna, Chairman, Hithkari Foundation, co- chaired this important session. The presentations in this session was given by Sri Vishwanath, Director, Biome Environmental Bangalore, on **“Water recycling and management in urban area”** and Dr H. P. Sumangala , Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore on **“Landscape gardening for environmental**

services”. Sri Vishwanath highlighted on sewage water recycling, development of urban watersheds and fostering urban biodiversity. Urban India needs policies for land and water use which have to be done in the short run. It is possible to link water, productive sanitation, waste management and horticulture in a cyclical consumption pattern, where the output becomes an input for the other sector. It is possible to find solutions at the household level and also at the city level. With intermediate steps also, many of the issues of water could be addressed. One such

example was presented *embedding food production as a part of the vast waste-water movement*

cycle of cities. These systems need to be better understood and tweaked to remove negative externalities of public health issues, if any. Dr. H.P. Sumangala, in her keynote presentation emphasized upon air and water pollution. She stressed the need for standardizing urban landscape models to achieve higher carbon sequestration. The session observed that urbanization has become necessity and reality. Hence, there is a need to address many issues and problems related to this sector. Research institutes have to address

issues like development of nutrient rich vegetable varieties, designer plants, development of protocol for terrace gardening and eco-friendly inputs. State horticulture departments have to start a separate section to address developmental programmes related to UPH. There is a need to start single window system for providing inputs required for the purpose.

TECHNICAL SESSION III

Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for complimenting the needs of food and nutrition

The third session was on Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for complementing the needs of food and nutrition. This session was chaired by Dr Rethinam, President CHAI, South Zone and former Director APCC. The session was co chaired by Shri S S Mehta, President, Anola Growers Association, Salem and Dr Akella Vani, Principal Scientist, IIHR.

The three keynote lecture in this session were presented by Dr A S Sidhu, Director, IIHR, Bangalore, Dr. P. Chowdappa, Principal Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore and Dr. A. Verghese, Principal Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore. Dr. A.S. Sidhu in his keynote lecture entitle **“Innovations in urban and Peri Urban Vegetable cultivation”**, emphasized on adopting of protected cultivation with mulch film and drip irrigation to increase yield, use of appropriate varieties of vegetables such as tomato that are indeterminate, and need for parthenocarpic cucumber, bitter gourd and muskmelon so that they can be grown in poly houses. He also brought in a novel concept of

grafting tomato on potato, cabbage on radish, and brinjal on potato, so that the yield from unit area can be increased. Machinery for grafting one lakh seedlings per hour exist, which can be utilized for enhancing the efficiency. Apart from this the importance of mechanization in peri-urban horticulture was also emphasized by Dr Sidhu.

Dr Chowdappa in his keynote lecture entitled **“Disease management in Urban Horticulture”** gave a graphic distribution of various diseases on horticultural crops and methods to control them by using chemicals as well as bio-control agents. The age old bordeaux mixture works best against a number of fungal pathogens and can easily be made at home and adopted for the management of diseases in urban and peri-urban horticulture. IIHR has developed and commercialized **Seed Pro**, a consortium of bio-control agents for the management of diseases which work excellently well for seed treatment. Dr Verghese, in his keynote presentation, entitled **“Pest management in urban and peri-urban horticulture”**, gave a brief account on different insect pests that occur in poly houses as well as in the fields around urban and peri-urban area. He also emphasized on the use of bio-control agents, neem cake and pongamia oil to control insect pests. Incorporating bird boxes and bird perches in home gardens brings in many insect eating birds such as the tailor bird that keep insects and caterpillars under check. The Chairman emphasized the need for vegetables and mushroom cultivation and and also a need for environment friendly management strategies.

TECHNICAL SESSION IV

Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for Economic Growth

This session was Chaired by Dr A S Sidhu, Director IIHR, and co-chaired by Dr Hanamashetti S I , Dean, KRC College of Horticulture and Dr A Verghese, Head, Division of Entomology and Nematology, IIHR, Bangalore. Three keynote lectures were presented, namely **“Waste management for urban horticulture”** by Dr Neelima Garg, Principal Scientist and

Head, Division of Post Harvest Management, CISH, Lucknow, **“Strawberry a choice fruit for urban and peri urban areas”** by Dr BNS Murthy, Principal Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore and Dr Vasantha Kumar presented a paper on **“Medicinal plants in urban and peri-urban horticulture”**. Dr Neelima Garg highlighted that

a huge amount of city waste is accumulating in urban areas, which needs to be reduced and utilized. Quoting, how mango peels can be used for pectin harvesting and vinegar making, she stressed how waste can be managed efficiently. Dr. BNS murthy in his keynote lecture, said that strawberry fruit is suited for urban and peri urban horticulture but need marketing strategies with

focus on urban market for quick marketing and consumption. He also mentioned about heart shaped ornamental strawberry which can be raised for valentine day. Talking about medicinal

plants , Dr Vasantha Kumar mentioned about their potential benefits such as aroma therapy in home gardens and explained how medicinal plants can be adopted in urban and peri-urban area for health care and to improve income. The session observed that urban and peri-urban horticulture is not only important for greening the cities to adopt to climate change but could be an activity for economic development, health care and employment.

TECHNICAL SESSION V

Plenary session and panel discussion

The session was chaired by Dr Prem Nath, Dr A S Sidhu and Dr P Retinam were the panelists. A plenary lecture entitled **“Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture for greening the cities, utilising the waste, meeting the needs and servicing the environment”** was delivered by Dr HP Singh, the Founder and Chairman, CHAI and former DDG (Hort.), ICAR. He stressed the need for horticulture

development and explained how horticulture is intellectually satisfying and economically rewarding. He traced back the development, provided data to show a many fold increase in production after enabling policy environment, investment and technological inputs. He stated that, production level of 245 million tonnes have been reached from 25 million tonnes in 1950, but we have to produce 340 million tonnes by 2020 to meet the growing demand with growth of health conscious population, urbanization and changing dietary needs. He also emphasised on importance of Horticulture as it contributes more than 30.4 percent to the GDP of Agriculture. He discussed about rapid urbanization and emphasised on need for UPH. He outlined the steps for greening the cities, utilising the waste, meeting the needs for fresh fruits and vegetables and servicing the environment. Initiatives taken by various organizations was also explained.

Finally, he presented many models of landscapes, terrace garden, rooftop gardens, vertical gardens, protected cultivation, waste utilization for mushroom production, and tree plantation. He concluded with optimism of UPH development for quality life of urban and peri-urban population. Contamination in sewage water, that is being used for watering horticulture crops has serious health risks and need attention to address the issue. The

The Chairman highly appreciated all the presentations, which covered all the aspects of Horticulture and its role in urban and peri-urban development including progress made in UPA. Once again he complimented the organizers and emphasized upon strong recommendations for research, development and policy. He stressed for the conversion of recommendations presented by co chairman of various technical sessions into action plan. The chairman wished that a strong movement for UPH is made in Bangalore, which should be exemplary for other cities. Formation of empowered inter-ministerial, inter-departmental and user group was also emphasised. The panelists strongly emphasized for the development of UPH, through technical inputs enabling policy and investment involving all stakeholders.

Recommendations of the workshop

Recommendations of the four technical sessions were presented by Dr N K Srinivash Rao, Dr M R Hegde, Dr Akela Vani and Dr A Vergese. After discussion and deliberations the following recommendations were adopted for its implementation:

1. *Recognising that the global population will double in 40 years, 10 billion people will live on the earth planet in 2050, of which 70 percent of the population shall live in cities and towns. Meeting the food and nutritional security with eco-friendly environment utilising natural resource in sustainable manner is a great challenge, which has attracted the attention of all the concerned, wherein Urban and Peri-Urban Agriculture (UPA) provide an option.*

2. *The urban population will increase more in developing countries, as a result of the immigration from rural areas, since people flock to the cities with the expectation of better quality of life in the cities and towns, expecting better opportunity in urban area. Options are to stop movement from rural to urban area or visualise that no efforts could stop migration and a rapid urbanisation is taking place demanding more food, water and living conditions in cities. If not planned and taken care, rapid urbanisation will lead to complexity of problems necessitating immediate action to develop urban peri-urban area liveable through UPH.*
3. *Urban and peri-urban horticulture (UPH) is the activities of greening the cities, utilising the waste, meeting the needs of food and nutrition, and servicing the environment by effective*

sustainable use of natural resources through technological inputs, investment and policy, bringing all the stakeholders together to work in a mission mode approach.

4. *Looking to the accelerated growth in population of cities and small towns in India, it could be expected that by 2050, more than 65 percent population will live in urban and peri-urban area demanding more food, nutrition and employment. With the current system of management, there will be more pollution to environment and will rapidly increase adding to climate change, bringing more challenges for the survival of mankind in the urban and peri-urban environment . Therefore, key challenge is to develop policy, strategies and technical support mechanisms for the sustainable management of urban and peri-urban horticulture, addressing production issues within a broader framework of environmental planning and management.*

5. *In the cities, environmental benefits and synergies can be achieved when horticulture is planned as a part of the urban landscape including safe recycling of solid waste and waste water. The country has responded to the needs for effective urban and peri-urban horticulture with emphasis on green space, green building, development of parks and gardens, and promotion of peri-urban vegetables production, but there continue to be a gap in integration. The design of UPH must include an element of urban and peri-urban horticulture aimed at improving access to food and advancing the livelihoods of people living in and around cities besides servicing the environment.*

6. *Horticulture is vital in urban and peri-urban areas to address the challenges emerging owing to rapid urbanisation of cities and small towns. Initiatives of peri-urban vegetables production alone cannot*

be enough for the dimension of challenges, which is complex and high in proportion. This necessitates holistic approaches having vertical and horizontal integration of the efforts of all the stakeholders, which should address all the links in chain of UPH development concurrently.

7. A focused attention to horticulture is needed not only for fruits and vegetables production, but for environmental services, and health care also. In the cities, zero land utilisation, interior and exterior landscaping, vertical garden, terrace cultivation of fruits and vegetables and mushroom culture must receive attention. Considering the necessity and urgency for UPH development, a policy framework is essential to

encourage all the stakeholders for urban and peri-urban horticulture. The policy must address research, development, partnership, desired networking and investment for UPH.

8. The workshop recognised the urgency and essentiality for the establishment of empowered committee involving different ministries and departments, as UPH needs support of various stakeholders. These empowered committees would capitalise on current knowledge and experiences of UPH and foster the initiatives through technological interventions, human resource development, awareness, enabling investment and networking.
9. Role of peri-urban horticulture in complementing the needs of food and nutrition should be emphasised. A model of terrace / roof garden should be set up and a systematic study for growing vegetables round the year, should be done through involvement of various development agencies. Mini kits with all materials such as sterilised soil, seeds and planting materials and biocontrol agents for growing a garden should be made available in stores.

10. Terrace gardening usually refer to the area in the immediate vicinity of a building. This is a raised ground space constructed around a dwelling house or on the sides of a hill. The terrace forms a link between the house and the rest of the outdoor living space and therefore must be designed in harmony with the plan of the house.
11. Roof garden is one of popular alternatives in urban and peri-urban areas because of the limited available space on the grounds of a house, particularly in the big cities and towns. The only space left for garden enthusiasts is the roof of the house and the balcony. To ensure the success of roof garden, technical and developmental support should be provided.
12. Plants offer environmental and ecological services along with aesthetic values. Trees and other ornamental plants are crucial to the sequestration of carbon from atmosphere, and play an important role in reducing carbon foot print. As such, trees and other landscape plants serve as an important tools in improving air quality of life in cities and mitigating potential health effects on human inhabitants. Therefore, zero land utilisation is inevitable to mitigate the climate change by reducing carbon loads in the cities through mass movement for tree planting with right choice of shrubs and trees.

13. Increasing competition for limited water resources in peri-urban areas has led to use of untreated waste water. Use of waste water is leading to high health risk due to heavy metals and harmful microbes. This need careful consideration for holistic approach in recycling or re-using of water through waste water treatments. The importance of waste water reuse in urban and peri-urban horticulture has to be recognised with clear policy guidelines. For better management

of park and gardens water has to be recycled by bio water treatment plant, as required quantity of water may not be available to meet irrigation needs.

14. *Urbanisation has become necessity and reality, which need technical inputs to the issues related with production and management. Hence, there is a need to address the issues and problems related to this sector through research. Research institutes have to address the issues like development of nutrient rich vegetable varieties, designer plants, development of protocol for terrace gardening and eco-friendly inputs. State horticulture departments have to start a separate section to address developmental programmes related to UPH. There is a need to start single window system for providing inputs required for the UPH.*

15. *Currently, a green space of 20 m² park as minimum standard has been suggested. There are city-specific specifications used to set standards. No dwelling should be more than 500 metres from a green area of atleast 6,000 m². Green spaces in*

urban systems should essentially be developed as networks. There is no definite standard for green space in city based on scientific data. Therefore, standard for green space in the cities and tree coverage need to be developed.

- 16. Climate change is expected to place increasing stress on urban and peri-urban areas. Green cities have become an option to mitigate the impact and adopt to climate change, as plants sequester the carbon dioxide and other gases. Well planned UPH could be an strategies to mitigate and adopt to the climate change. Therefore, all the initiatives must be taken for the development of UPH.*

Conclusion and appreciations

Dr H P Singh, in his concluding remarks briefly outlined the outcomes of the workshop. He said that ensuring adequate food supply, reduction in environmental pollution, employment and income generation are some of the important facets of urban and peri-urban horticulture (UPH). In the current scenario of changing

dietary habits with increasing income, there is a growing demand for horticultural produce. At the same time, population pressure in urban and peri-urban area is increasing at accelerated rate and it is visualized that, more than 65 percent people in India will live in cities and towns by 2050. This is a great challenge and needs attention for optimal management of urban and peri-urban resources by viewing horticulture as an integral component of the urban natural resource system. This would balance the competitive and synergistic interactions among the users of the natural resources (water, land, air, wastes). Benefits of appropriate management include improved hydrological functioning through soil and water conservation, micro-climate improvements, avoided costs of disposal of the recycled urban wastes (waste water and solid waste), improved biodiversity, and greater recreational and aesthetic values of green space. When we look back, it is evident that urban and peri-urban activities for gardening interior and exterior landscaping, terrace garden by amateurs, parks, landscapes in water body and growing of vegetables and flowers adjacent to cities have been practiced, but need scientific approaches. Interest in UPH is increasing not only to utilise the space but for social and economic reasons also. With accelerated awareness, UPH could be a reality to address the challenges, which is posed by rapid urbanization in developing nations. Dr Singh, thanked the experts for their excellent coverage in the presentation and distinguished experts for chairing and co-chairing the technical sessions. He also appreciated the participation of Dr N K Krishna Kumar, DDG (Hort.), ICAR. Special thanks were extended to Dr Prem Nath for his untiring support to the organization of the workshop, by Dr Singh. He also thanked the dignitaries for their active support in organisation of this National Workshop. Dr. Singh also highlighted activities of CHAI and its recognition in India and abroad. Finally, he thanked core group of organizers, especially Dr Chowdappa, Dr Kariyana and Dr H P Sumangla.

The National workshop concluded with vote of thanks to dignitaries, learned speakers, chair and co-chair, distinguished delegates and the organizations which supported the event, by Dr H P Sumangla, local organizing secretary and scientist, IIHR, Bangalore. She also thanked all those who were associated, directly or indirectly for the success of the National Workshop and said

that this initiative of CHAI would go a long way in greening the cities, meeting the needs, utilising the waste and servicing the environment.

Business meet discussed all the facets in converting the development of UPH as a business opportunity for designers, nursery men and inputs providers. The Chairman, CHAI, ensured to provide all the help for the cause of UPH. He also thanked all the participants for their interest in UPH.

Programme	
8.30 am - 9.30 am	Registration
9.30 am - 10.15 am	Introductory session
Welcome	Dr. P. Rethinam , President CHAI, South Zone (Former Executive Director APCC Jakarta)
Remarks by	Dr. A.S. Sidhu , Director, IIHR, Bangalore.
Address by Chief Guest	Dr. N.K. Krishna Kumar , DDG (Hort.), ICAR, New Delhi
Introductory Remarks	Dr. Prem Nath , Founder and Chairman PNAS Foundation, Bangalore
Chairmans Remarks	Dr. H.P. Singh , Founder and Chairman Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India (CHAI)
Vote of Thanks	Dr. P. Chowdappa , President, Karnataka Unit (CHAI)
10.15 am - 10.30 am	Tea Break
10.30 am - 12.00 noon	TECHNICAL SESSION 1
Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for Greening the Cities	
Chairman	Dr. H.P. Singh , Founder and Chairman Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India (CHAI)
Co-Chairman	Dr. N.L. Patel , Dean, NAU, Navsari, Gujarat
Co-Chairman	Dr. N.K. Srinivas Rao , Emeritus Scientist IIHR Bangalore.
Keynote lectures	Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture - A Global Perspective Dr. Prem Nath
	Environmental challenges and emerging Landscape Solution Robert Fernandez
	Discussion

12.00 noon - 1.00 pm TECHNICAL SESSION II	
Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for environmental services	
Chairman	Dr. P. Rethinam, President, CHAI, South Zone
Co-Chairman	Dr. M.R. Hegde Chairman, RMCC, IIHR, Bangalore.
Co-Chairman	Dr. Kariyanna, MD, Hithkari Nursery, Bangalore
Keynote lectures	Water recycling and management in Urban Area Shri Vishwanath Director, Biome environmental, Bangalore
	Landscape gardening for environmental Services. Dr. H. P. Sumangla Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore
	Discussion
1.00 pm -2.00 pm.	Lunch Break
2.00 pm -3.00 pm TECHNICAL SESSION III	
Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture for complimenting the needs of food and nutrition	
Chairman	Dr. P. Rethinam President CHAI, South Zone (Former Executive Director APCC Jakarta)
Co-Chairman	Shri. S.S. Mehta President, Anola Growers Associations, Salem.
Co-Chairman	Dr. Akela Vani Principal Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore
Keynote lectures	Innovations in Urban and PeriUrban Vegetable cultivation Dr. A.S. Sidhu Director, IIHR, Bangalore.

	<p>Disease management in Urban Horticulture Dr. P. Chowdappa Principal Scientist IIHR, Bangalore</p>
	<p>Pest management in Urban Horticulture Dr. A. Verghese Principal Scientist and Head, IIHR, Bangalore</p>
	<p>Discussion</p>
3.00 pm - 4.00 pm	TECHNICAL SESSION IV
Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture for Economic Growth	
Chairman	Dr. A.S. Sidhu Director IIHR, Bangalore
Co-Chairman	Dr. Hanumashetty S.I. Dean Horticulture, KRC ARABHAVI, UHS
Co-Chairman	Dr. A. Verghese Principal Scientist and Head IIHR
Keynote lectures	<p>Waste management for urban horticulture Dr. Neelima Garg Principal Scientist and Head, CISH, Lucknow</p>
	<p>Strawberry – a choice Fruit Crop for Urban Peri-urban Areas Dr. B.N.S. Murthy Principal Scientist, IIHR, Bangalore</p>
	<p>Medicinal plants in Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture Dr. Vasantha Kumar, Principal Scientist and Head, IIHR, Bangalore</p>
	<p>Discussion</p>

4.00 pm - 5.00 pm PANEL DISCUSSION AND PLENARY SESSION	
Chairman	Dr. Prem Nath Chairman, PNAS Foundation
Panelists	Dr. P. Rethenam President, Southen Zone CHAI
	Dr. A.S. Sidhu Director, IIHR, Bangalore
Plenary Lecture	Urban And PeriUrban Horticulture for Greening the cities utilizing waste, meeting the needs and servicing the environment Dr. H.P. Singh Founder and Chairman CHAI and former DDG (Hort.)
Panel Discussion Panalists	Dr. Prem Nath Dr. H.P. Singh Dr. P. Rethinam Dr. A.S. Sidhu
Presentations of Reports of Technical sessions I, II, III and IV Dr. N.K. Srinivash Rao Dr. M.R. Hegde Dr. Akela Vani Dr. A. Vergese	
Discussion, resolutions and adoptions of Recomendations and Banglore declaration on UPH	
Concluding Remarks	Dr. H.P. Singh Founder and Chairman, CHAI
Vote of Thanks	Dr. H.P. Sumangala Organizing Secretary
5.00 pm - 5.45 pm	High Tea
6.00 pm - 6.30 pm	Business Meet Under the Chairmanship of Chairman CHAI

Confederation of Horticulture Associations of India
(Reg. under section 25 of the companies Act, 1956 and ISO 9001:2008)

Bangalore Declaration

On Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture (UPH) for greening the cities, utilizing the waste, meeting the needs and servicing the environment.

Recognizing that global population will reach 10 billion by the end of 2050, of which, about 70 percent of people shall reside in urban and peri-urban areas, there is a global concern to meet their needs for food, nutrition and eco-environment. In this context, Urban and Peri-Urban Agriculture (UPA) is emerging as one of the options. Considering that, horticulture has to play a pivotal role in UPA, for greening the cities and towns, meeting the needs of fresh produce, utilizing home waste and above all to service the environment, National Workshop Resolved that: Urban and Peri-Urban horticulture (UPH) is the activities of greening the cities, utilizing the waste, meeting the needs of food and nutrition, and servicing the environment by effective and sustainable use of natural resources through technological inputs, investment and policy. The workshop identified the key challenges and resolved that there is an urgent need to develop policy, strategies and technical support mechanisms for the sustainable management of urban and peri-urban horticulture, addressing production issues within a broader framework of environmental planning and management. In urban and peri-urban areas, horticulture is not only for the fruits and vegetables production, but also for environmental services and health care. The workshop recognized the urgency and essentiality for the establishment of empowered committee involving different ministries and departments, as UPH needs support of various stakeholders. These empowered committees would capitalize on current knowledge and experiences of UPH and foster the initiatives through technological interventions, human resource development, awareness, enabling investment and net working. The workshop also resolved that there is need for research support to address the technological challenges in urban and peri-urban horticulture. Green cities have become an option to mitigate the impact and adapt to climate change, as plants sequester the carbon dioxide and other gases. Well planned UPH could be a strategy to mitigate and adapt to the climate change. Therefore, all the initiatives must be taken for the development of UPH. Finally, the workshop expressed the optimism that: committed development of urban and peri-urban Horticulture with accelerated awareness could prove to be an effective vehicle to address the challenges, which is posed by rapid urbanization in developing nations.

The declaration made on 2nd march, 2013, in the National workshop on Urban and Peri-Urban Horticulture, held at Bangalore.

Ogranisers

Dr H.P. Singh, with rare combination of scientific excellence, conscientious administration, dynamic management skills and academic depth, in a career spanning 42 years, a prime mover of research, development and education, has served horticulture/agriculture in various capacities namely, Scientist, Project Coordinator (Fruits); Director, NRC for Banana; Horticulture Commissioner, Govt. of India; Chairman, Coconut Development Board; Dean (Agriculture), GBPUA&T, Pantnagar; Vice-Chancellor, RAU, Pusa; Deputy Director General (Horticulture), ICAR, and now, he is the Founder and Chairman of Confederation of Horticulture Associations

of India (CHAI). Additionally, he also served as DDG (Ag Extn.), MS, NCPH, Director Hort. and others. He occupied positions in many international organisations like the Chairman of APCC, Jakarta, National Director for internationally-aided projects and Chairperson of Steering Committee, BAPNET, Bioversity International. He formulated and implemented various international programmes. With excellent academic record, Dr Singh has outstandingly contributed to research, education and development, which earned him 3 international, 36 national awards and 9 fellowships including the Fellow of NAAS. He has developed many cultivars and technologies which has impacted the horticulture. Recognising his immense contribution, OUAT, Bhubaneswar, has conferred him D.Sc. (Honoris causa). Dr Singh, the architect of National Horticulture Mission, starting from planning to execution, has transformed Indian horticulture. He has authored and edited 57 books, 30 bulletins, 40 reports and over 350 scientific papers and is widely traveled in India and abroad and has peer recognition in international community. Many high powered committees, both at national and international level, have been headed by him to provide solutions to the challenges. His efforts have provided a strong foundation for horticultural development, leading to Golden Revolution in India. Visionary approach with zeal and commitment for achieving excellence and exemplary skills in management of Dr Singh has brought dynamisms to the positions which ever, wherever, he held. Initiative of NanoTech in Agriculture by the ICAR is credited to Dr Singh. As the Founder and Chairman of CHAI, Dr Singh is committed to science and technology-led development by providing professional solutions to the emerging challenges.

Dr. H.P. Sumangala, Scientist, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bangalore with expertise in landscape gardening and floriculture has developed alternate cropping systems for Peri-Urban and introduced concept of combating indoor air pollution by foliage plants and also wild / native plants for landscaping. More than 47 articles including 6 book chapter, three books are to her credit. She had honour of invitation for the presentation of her concepts by then Honorable President of India, Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam. She is member in many committees on beautification and landscape gardening. As an organizing secretary, she organized National consultation on Landscape Gardening for Aesthetic Values and Environmental services (2010). National workshop on Urban and Peri Urban Horticulture (2011). She is Fellow and executive member of Indian Society of Ornamental Crops, New Delhi. She is fellow of Confederation of Horticultural Association of India. She is recipient of many awards for her papers.

Dr. P. Chowdappa, Principal Scientist, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bangalore, worked at CABI Bioscience, UK on molecular biology of Phytophthora diseases of plantation crops. As a National Network Coordinator, ALCOCERA, he is coordinating research on *Alternaria*, *Colletotrichum* and *Cercospora* diseases of field and horticultural crops, operating at 16 centers to develop cutting edge technologies for effective management of the diseases across the crops and regions in India. He has developed diagnostic kits for rapid detection of *Alternaria solani* in tomato, *Colletotrichum capsici* in chilli, seeds and Seed Pro- a microbial growth promoter and

fungal disease suppressor which has been commercialized. He has published more than 50 research papers, 22 book chapters, 03 experimental manuals, 16 technical bulletins, 03 extension folders, 19 popular articles and 4 books. He was a member National Steering Committee on Cocoa, Coordinator, Cocoa phytophthora and expert Committee Member in Coffee wilt. Awarded DFID and BSPP, UK and Best Student, poster and oral presentation awards by Indian Phytopathological Society, New Delhi and Society for Promotion of Horticulture, Bangalore. He is president of CHAI, Karnataka Unit.

Dr. Kariyanna, Managing Director, Hithkari Foundation Bangalore, has been involved in the development of horticulture through adoption of improved and scientific technologies. He has adopted drip irrigation/fertigation, high density planting and precision farming in his own farm. He has established a hightech nursery and tissue culture lab and is supplying quality planting materials to the farmers for the last two decades. He has been guiding and motivating farmers to adopt scientific practices and has become an inspiration for the farming community. He was a member of RAC, IIHR, Bangalore and is also in advisory executive committees of national and state level development departments as well as farmers organisations. His services in horticulture/agriculture for the benefit of all types of farmers in the Karnataka state and in the country are widely appreciated.